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The history of Central Asian studies in France actually goes back to the 18th century. In this regard, Joseph Degin's *L'histoire des Huns, des Turcs, des Mogols et autres Tartares* (history of the Huns, Turks, Mongols and other Tartars), who taught at the Collège de France, can be said from the earliest studies of the history of the region (Ostonov 2023). Thus a scientific interest in the region has begun. Collège de France can be seen as the first institution to begin the study of the history of the region. However, it was not until 1911 that the department, which specifically researched and studied Central Asia, was established. The department was headed by the Chinese studies scholar, Paul Pelliot. The department, then named *Langues, histoire et archéologie de l'Asie centrale*, operated until 1945. From 1965, it was renamed and Louis Hambis was appointed leader. This time the department was named *Langues, histoire et archéologie de l'Asie centrale*. This activity lasted until 1977 (Römer 2023 : 627-660). These two departments relied primarily on Chinese sources in their studies on Central Asian history. Paul Pelliot, for example, acted as a Chinese scholar and conducted scientific research on the history of the region based on Chinese sources. This was naturally dominated by the Chinese point of view. The studies at the college did not stop ever. The college focused on the region again around 2013. From this year, another department began to work under the name *Histoire et cultures de l'Asie centrale préislamique*. Franz Grenet leads it. Unlike its predecessors, then the department is trying to explore Central Asia from within, relying on its local sources. In addition, the factors that created the conditions for this, we can cite archaeological missions in the region, historical sources found throughout the 20th century and works of art (Grenet 2014).

Translation of works on the history of the region

Throughout the 19th century, the Asian Society placed great emphasis on the work of publishing sources related to Central Asia in French. At the beginning of this movement stood Charles Defremery. After publishing excerpts from Abdurahman Jami's "Bahoristan" in 1842, both in French and in the original textual language, from a number of other works on the history of the region, he succeeded in publishing excerpts from works on the history of a number of other regions, both in French and in the language of the original text. For example, parts of Hamdullah Mustauf's "History of Guzida" about the Seljuks and Ismailis (*Histoire des Seldjoukides et des Ismaéliens ou Assassins de l'Iran, extraits du Tarikhi Guzideh d'Hamd-Allah Mustaufi, Paris : Imprimerie nationale. 1848*), parts of Mirkhond's "Rawzat us Safa" about the history of Khorezmshahs (*Histoire des sultans du Kharezm, par Mirkhond. Texte persan, accompagné de notes historiques, géographiques et philologiques, Paris. 1842*) and Samanids (*Histoire des Samanides, par Mirkhond. Texte persan, traduit et accompagné de notes critiques, historiques et géographiques, Paris 1845*), parts of Khondamir's "Habib us Siyar" about Mongol Khans in Turkestan (Defremery, C. *Histoire des Khans mongols du Turkistan et de la Transoxiane, extraite du "Habib Essier" de Khondemir, traduite du persan et accompagnée de notes, Paris, 1852*), Ibn Battuta's travels around Central Asia (*Voyages d'Ibn-Bartoutah dans la Perse, l'Asie Centrale et l'Asie Mineure, 1853—1859*), were published on the pages of *Journal Asiatique*, the main publication of the society with the translation and the original text. (Finot 1922 : 152-153)

The director of the school of oriental languages, the eminent Orientalist Charles Schefer, also conducted research and published on a number of sources on the history of Central Asia. He translated

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY**VOLUME-5, ISSUE-5**

Mir Abdulkarim Bukhari's work in Istanbul, dedicated to the history of Central Asia, into French and published it with the original text. (*Histoire de l'Asie centrale, de 1153 à 1233 de l'hégire, par Mir Abdul Kérim Boukhari, 2 vol. in-8°, 1876*). Furthermore, he made several publications available to the French scientific community and contributed to the enrichment of the school library, including Rizokulikhan's relations with Khwarezm (*Relation de l'Ambassade au Kharezm (Khiva), par Riza Quly Khan, 2 vol. in-8°, 1879*), travel through Central Asia (*Différents itinéraires dans l'Asie centrale, in-8°, 1878*), Narshakhi's "The history of Bukhara" (*Description topographique et historique de Boukhara, par Mohammed Nerchakhy, in-8°, 1892*) (Finot 1922: 186).

It seems that the studies carried out during this period are based mainly on written sources and consist mainly of translations and commentaries on them. Looking at the sources of research, it consists mainly of Chinese and domestic written sources. Later, the archaeological studies carried out in the region caused a significant increase in sources. In particular, the discovery of Sogdian and Bactrian inscriptions provided new information and sources.

Archeological missions

In this case, a little more attention is paid to archaeological excavations in Central Asia, in particular, to French missions. Central Asia began to open to the world in the 19th century. The imperialist movements of the British and Russian empires also motivated this. A large part of Central Asia, other than Afghanistan, was conquered by Russia. Afghanistan remained heavily influenced by the United Kingdom. Neither Afghanistan, nor Bukhara, Turkestan, Khiva, influenced by the Russian Empire, had the opportunity to fully open up for foreigners, nor could foreigners come freely. (*Gorshenina 2013 : 25-40*)

In the last quarter of the 19th century, only a few French tourists visited the area as tourists, while foreigners operating in the region for scientific purposes were not at all. Archaeological research was carried out mainly during the Soviet period. The first movement in Central Asia within the French missions, the DAFA (Délégation archéologique française en Afghanistan), began its activities in 1922. It was founded by Alfred Fusher, led by Joseph Hakin in 1933-1941, and Roman Girshman in 1941-1943. This mission conducted archaeological research in several areas of Afghanistan. Having carried out excavations in areas such as Bactria, Hadda, Oyhanim, DAFA was forced to complete its activities from 1982 as a result of the war started in the country. (*Gorshenina 2013 : 25-40*)

Afghanistan was not peaceful then and DAFA decided to move north. Cooperation with Soviet scientists allowed them to study civilizations north of Amurdarya. In 1982, a scientific conference with the cooperation of Soviet-French scientists was organized in Dushanbe. French archaeologists thus penetrated Soviet territory. This cooperation, with which Tajikistan began, also penetrated into the territory of Uzbekistan. The Sarazm settlement near Panjikent began to be explored from 1984 and was the first excavation in a French-Tajik collaboration. Beginning in 1989, however, the French-Uzbek archaeological mission MAFOuz (Mission archéologique franco-ouzbek de Sogdian) began to study Afrosiab. The mission was led by Frantz Grenet, a disciple of Mikhail Masson, a prominent archaeologist by France, who in turn was known as the founder of Uzbek archaeology, and Muhammadjan Isomiddinoy, an archaeologist by Uzbekistan. Thus, many archaeological sites of Uzbekistan were excavated and studied by this mission. In addition to F. Grené, notable French archaeologists such as Claude Rapin, Julie Valle Rayevsky, Étienne Delavesier, Paul Bernard participated in the excavations. Another mission was established in southern Uzbekistan, responsible for studying the ancient Bactrian culture. This mission was led by Pierre Lerisch and Shokir Pidayev. Another mission in Bukhara was also engaged in the study of the Bukhara Oasis (*Ostonov 2023: 47-*

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-5

50). In addition to Tajikistan and Uzbekistan, French archaeologists have been and are working in Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Turkmenistan. The information gained from the activities of the French archaeological missions revealed new directions and themes in Central Asian studies in France and made France one of the leaders in the field in the region.

IFEAC - exploring the region from within

In the exploration of Central Asia, IFEAC (Institut français d'études sur l'Asie Centrale), established in Tashkent in 1993, started a new era. The IFEAC, the only institution of this type in the region, played an important role in the internationalization of studies on Central Asia, providing a link between the academic circles of Central Asia and the academic circles of France, Europe and North America. In the 1990s-2000s, the rich library, the regular publication of the journal *Cahiers d'Asie Centrale*, as well as its first directors' (P. Chuvin, V. Furniau, R. Dor, B. Balci) actions allowed IFEAC France to be at the centre of the region's research system. For a period when communication and information circulation were not as fast as today, this was a good result. In France, research on Central Asia is conducted in many research groups. The reason for this is the geographical dispersion of employment and the dispersion of research units. Currently, scientists researching the region operate in about forty laboratories. Unlike IFEAC, not a single laboratory deals exclusively with Central Asia, but studies among other areas. In the late 2000s, a scientific laboratory for the study of Central Asia was established under the CNRS (Centre National de la recherche scientifique - National Centre for scientific research), but changes in the management of the Centre stopped its activity. The center has been operating in Bishkek since 2010¹.

Laboratories and centers

Currently, groups including Central Asia are operating in a number of institutions. They are laboratories that work in collaboration with the following French research centers and universities: CETOBAC (Centre d'études turques, ottomanes, balkaniques et centrasiatiques - UMR 8032 CNRS, EHESS, Collège de France), CeRMI (Centre de recherche sur le monde iranien - UMR 8041 CNRS, Paris 3 Sorbonne nouvelle, EPHE, INALCO), CERCEC (Centre d'études des mondes russe, centre-européen et caucasien - UMR 8083 CNRS, EHESS), AOROC (Archéologie et Philologie d'Orient et d'Occident - UMR 8546 CNRS, ENS, EPHE), Éco-Anthropologie (UMR 7206 CNRS, MNHN), ARSCAN (Archéologies et sciences de l'Antiquité - UMR 7041 CNRS, Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne, Paris Nanterre), GSRL (Groupe Sociétés, Religions, Laïcités - UMR 8582 CNRS, EPHE), CREE (Centre de recherche Europe-Eurasie - EA 4513 INALCO), Eur'Orbem (Cultures et sociétés d'Europe orientale, balkanique et médiane - UMR 8224 CNRS, Sorbonne université) (*Gorshenina 2012*)

In 2014, the Sorbonne-Kazakhstan Institute was established in Almaty as part of a partnership between the Sorbonne University of France and the National Pedagogical University of Kazakhstan named after Abay. But this institution did not operate as expected. When we looked at the official website of the Institute, we witnessed that the main page of the site has not been updated since 2022 (<https://sorbonne.kz/fr/>). Most of the Central Asian studies are conducted in institutions located in Paris. Two-thirds of researchers-professors work in Paris laboratories (*Thorez, Cleuziou, and Fauve 2021:15*)

Problems

¹ <https://ifeac.hypotheses.org/institut/structure>

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-5

In France, Central Asian studies are attracting fewer professionals compared to other areas. Building an accurate list of researchers by region now presents a challenge as they are operating in a scattered manner, as well as at one point doing research in other directions. Nevertheless, it is not impossible. The number of researchers-profesors working on Central Asia consists of almost 60. Of these, 14 were involved in the history of the region and 12 in the archaeology. (*Thorez, Cleuziou, Fauve 2021:11*) There are also a number of researchers working in geography, anthropology, sociology, economics, art history, political science, demography, etc. In France in the last decade, CNRS as well as a number of universities (U. de Versailles Saint-Quentin, U. Paris 8, U. Paris Sud, U. Lyon 2, INALCO) employed researchers in a number of fields. O. Bordeaux, Y.Karyev, J.Lyuilye from archaeology, G.Shomentovsky, S.Gorshenina, M.Tutan from history, J.Cleuziu from anthroplogy, L.Direnberger from sociology are conducting research on the region and teaching students. It should be noted that since 2013 **he** has been heading and teaching the «Histoires et cultures de l'asie centrale pré-islamique» (History and culture of Central Asia in pre-Islamic period) at the Collège de France². There is another aspect of the issue that studies related to this archeology may have a problem. This was followed by the death of one after another of a generation of major French archaeologists who were internationally recognized and worked effectively in exactly the five Central Asian republics (P.Bernard, R.Besenwal, P.Chuvin, and O.Lecompt). The Foreign Ministry's overseas excavations Commission report, published in 2019, noted that the Commission now stated that it does not support archaeological excavations in either Kazakhstan or Kyrgyzstan³.

Research focusing on the region now focuses more on modern times. In particular, modern history, anthorpology, sociology, political science, are attracting more moderate. The topics that scientists refer to also come from an existing context. In particular, it is engaged in research on such topics as the construction of the state and society, the new Great Silk Road, the management of Natural Resources, Development and provides state organizations and the private sector with expert conclusions. But some areas (such as economic history, cultural geography, linvistics, law), some topics (such as labor, poverty, social group and strata for the modern era), some periods (Shaybanids, Ashtarkhanids), some regions (Turkmenistan, pre-colonized Kazakh steppes) are little studied or not studied at all. Problems in this regard also depend on the issue of training personnel. Even the organization of classes and special seminars in a number of institutions does not completely eliminate this problem. For example, despite the fact that INALCO has a seminar on the language of chigatay, the study of the languages of Central Asia is not carried out at a sufficient level. They are often taught next to Persian or Turkish. In addition, not a single university in France operates research-teachers on the modern history of Central Asia (*Thorez, Cleuziou, and Fauve 2021: 15*).

The international openness of the research is another outstanding feature of the ongoing research on the region, in addition to the collaboration developed with Central Asian colleagues. Researchers have established thick relationships with colleagues working in centers located in Europe, America and Asia in the direction of all disciplines. As a result of this cooperation, Common Projects and duplications are carried out. In France, employees and researchers from outside Europe are less likely to be employed in research on Central Asia than in other destinations and other countries. Currently, the only scientific researcher from the region for Central Asia in France is working at CNRS. Svetlana

² <https://www.college-de-france.fr/fr/chaire/frantz-grenet-histoire-et-cultures-de-asie-centrale-preislamique-chaire-statutaire>

³ Cartographie stratégique des missions archéologiques françaises à l'étranger (2018-2022) // https://www.diplomatie.gouv.fr/IMG/pdf/meae_archeo_web_cle05c258-1.pdf

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-5

Gorshenina is originally from Uzbekistan⁴. There is not an employee from Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan (*Thorez, Cleuziou, and Fauve 2021:16*). This situation encourages French scientific research and higher education institutions to increase their attractiveness and consider the issue of revising recruitment policies.

Researchs on the region in scientific journals

There are also several scientific publications on Central Asia. Let's get to know a few of them. Among these journals, we can only cite one journal that publishes articles about the region. The IFEAC's scientific publication, the Cahier d'Asie Centrale is distinguished only by the fact that it publishes research on the region⁵. Therefore, if we pay attention to the main directions to which the journal refers. The journal is an annual journal and is published once each year as part of a special topic. We can divide the articles published in the journal into five areas. These include post-Soviet states' development and politics, anthropology and ethnology, history and archaeology, socio-economic studies, security, and geopolitical issues. The journal can publish articles not only by French researchers, but also by experts from all over the world. Articles may also be devoted to individual states in the region, or cover general area issues. The articles consist mainly of research in the socio-humanitarian fields. According to the magazine's website, its latest 28th issue was published in 2020 under the editorship of Catherine Pujol. (*Poujol 2020*)

The next scientific journal that publishes research on Central Asia is Cahiers du Monde russe⁶. This interdisciplinary journal provides research on the political, social, economic, cultural, and especially literary history of the Russian Empire (from its inception until 1917), the USSR, and the countries that arose after it. One of the peculiarities of the magazine is that special attention is paid to the study of the Empire and the USSR in its national, religious and cultural components. Almost a third of the articles are devoted to individual territories of the former USSR: the Caucasus, Central Asia, Tatarstan and Crimea. The journal has a permanent team of authors abroad and in France. Articles and reviews are accepted in French, Russian and English. The journal started out as early as 1959 and was known as "Cahiers du Monde russe et soviétique" until 1993. And since 1994 it was renamed «Cahiers du Monde russe. Russie, Empire russe, Union soviétique, États indépendants (ISSN 1252-6576)».

The next scientific journal is Journal asiatique. It has been published since 1822 and mainly publishes research on Asia. The journal is the official publication of the Asian society. It publishes articles in French, Spanish, English, German and Italian⁷.

The next scientific journal on Central Asia is Études Mongoles & Sibériennes, Centrasiatiques & Tibétaines (EMSCAT)⁸. The journal was established in 1970. It is also known by name that it publishes scientific articles mainly on the Mongols, peoples of Siberia, Central Asia and Tibet. The journal accepts and publishes articles in French and English from different countries.

Studies in Central Asia are also published in Revue des mondes musulmans et de la Méditerranée (abbreviated REMMM)⁹. Because the region is considered one of the most important parts of the Islamic world. The journal presents research on the entire Muslim world in the form of thematic issues. In the form of two parts, «History» and «Modern World», it publishes scientific articles and

⁴ <https://www.svetlana-gorshenina.net/untitled>

⁵ <https://journals.openedition.org/asiacentrale/>

⁶ <https://journals.openedition.org/monderusse/4242>

⁷ https://poj.peeters-leuven.be/content.php?journal_code=JA&url=journal

⁸ <https://journals.openedition.org/emscat/>

⁹ <https://www.iremam.cnrs.fr/fr/la-remmm>

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-5

researches about the Muslim world by mature scientists of the West and East in the socio-humanitarian direction. The articles published in REMMM are mainly on topics such as history, political science, anthropology, sociology, geography, etc¹⁰.

The next scientific journal is «Turcica. Revue d'études turques, peuples, langues, cultures, États»¹¹. The Journal is an international interdisciplinary journal that publishes scientific articles on the Turkish world in German, English, French, and Italian. The journal is published once a year. As we can see, this journal also publishes garden scientific goals with the history of Central Asia. The director of the journal is the French Egyptologist, Orientalist Marc Toutan¹².

Archaeology is also an important branch in the studies on Central Asian history. A number of French archaeologists have written about the archaeology of the region. The scientific news gained here has been published extensively in the *Revue archéologique*, published in France. The journal is considered one of the oldest in France. Originally limited only to the territory of France, the Journal has since expanded and adapted to publish research mainly on antiquity. It is the only Journal of Archaeology in France that looking back at its geography, covers Greece, Rome, Iberia, Central Asia and other regions, starting with France. It pays great attention to sculpture, painting, pottery, small objects, architecture, urban planning, historical, social, geographical problems related to archaeology, epigraphy and studies on ancient Latin and Greek texts. The journal accepts articles mainly in French. However, articles in English, Spanish, German, and Italian can also be accepted¹³.

All of the above journals are published in France and all have access to open access on the Internet. Within the framework of the open science policy of the French National Center for Scientific Research (CNRS), all scientific articles published by laboratories, institutes, centers under the management of the center are placed in electronic ones in open access¹⁴. Scientific articles by French researchers can also be found on the portal Cairn.info, which operates in French. The Portal was founded in 2005 and operates in cooperation with scientific centers in France. Of this some, adapted mainly to the socio-humanitarian sciences, more than 360 thousand scientific articles, and more than 18 thousand scientific books can now be found. 72 % of the articles are free to download. More than 50 scientific journals in France cooperate with the Portal today. More than 30,000 scientific works have been found in response to a search survey of Central Asia¹⁵.

Dissertations

The main starting point of scientific research is dissertations. Regarding dissertations, it can be said that from 2010 to 2023, the number of dissertations about the region is about 70. Topics of work within this period included political science, history, anthropology, archaeology, and economics. (*Thorez, Cleuziou, Fauve 2021: 22*) In comparison, 98 cases were defended by region in France between 1991 and 2007 (*Gorshenina 2012*). It appears that the number of works defended in the last twenty years has declined, though not very large. It has also been virtually unexplored in the fields of modern history, anthropology, and geography.

Effects of local conditions

¹⁰ <https://journals.openedition.org/remmm/>

¹¹ https://poj.peeters-leuven.be/content.php?journal_code=TURC&url=journal

¹² <https://www.college-de-france.fr/fr/personne/marc-toutant>

¹³ <https://www.jstor.org/journal/revuearch>

¹⁴ <https://www.cnrs.fr/fr/cnrsinfo/le-cnrs-se-desabonne-de-la-base-de-publications-scopus>

¹⁵ https://www.cairn.info/resultats_recherche.php?searchTerm=Asie+centrale+

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY**VOLUME-5, ISSUE-5**

The state of research on Central Asia is also influenced in its own way by the circumstances of the region. The political conjuncture in the states of the region, the working conditions associated with political orientation, the state of their relations with France have their influence in the course of research. Nevertheless, France maintains its image well before the eyes of the states of the region. When considering the conditions caused by the Covid-19 pandemic, the conditions of entry into the territory of the country of Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan eased in the last years. For example, the visa restriction was partially lifted in Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan. For French citizens, there is an opportunity to stay on the territory of these countries without a visa for up to 30 days. Research institutions in Central Asia, on the other hand, need international cooperation. Kazakhstan and France have signed a number of agreements on cooperation in mutual research. Uzbekistan has also undertaken a number of collaborative projects with France in the scientific and cultural fields. For example, from November 2022 to March 2023, an exhibition dedicated to the history of Uzbekistan was presented at the Louvre Museum. As part of this exhibition, a collection-catalog was also published with the participation of French and Uzbek scientists, as well as scientists from other countries (*Rante, Lintz 2022*). The book contains scientific articles on the history of Central Asia from ancient times to the 16th century.

Conclusion

In France, the evolution of Central Asian studies has been manifested through various scientific and institutional changes over the decades. Since 1990, we can see that research on the region has been slowly but continuously developing in France. These studies focus on the historical, cultural and socio-political dynamics of the Central Asian states, covering various disciplines such as history, ethnology, linguistics, political science, archaeology and religious studies. The contribution of a number of scientific centers in France to the study of the region has been invaluable. Collège de France has played and is playing an important role in the development of research on the region with its centre for Indian and Central Asian Studies. Also, the school of Advanced Studies in the Social Sciences (EHESS), through its Center for Russian, Caucasian, Eastern European and Central Asian Studies (CERCEC) and the Center for Turkish, Ottoman, Balkan and Central Asian countries (CETOBaC), has contributed significantly to the study of the region. In addition to these, we have also cited a number of scientific centers above that also show enthusiasm in conducting research on Central Asia. Studies on Central Asian, which had been actively developed in the 19th and early 20th centuries, had also been active for some time between the 1990s and 2000s.

REFERENCES

- Ostonov 2023* – *Ostonov J.* Eftaliylar davrining fransuz sharqshunosligida o'rganilishiga doir (On the study of the Ephthalites period in French oriental studies) // Research Focus International Scientific Journal. Volume 2 | Issue 9. Tashkent 2023 // <https://refocus.uz/index.php/1/article/view/448/321>
- Grenet 2014* – *Grenet F.* Recentrer l'Asie centrale : Leçon inaugurale prononcée le jeudi 7 novembre 2013. Paris. Collège de France, 2014. Web. <https://books.openedition.org/cdf/3590>
- Finot 1922* – *Finot L.* Historique de la Société Asiatique // Le livre du centenaire (1822-1922). Paris, 1922
- Gorshenina 2013* – *Gorshenina S.* L'archéologie française dans l'Asie centrale soviétique et post-soviétique // Cahier d'Asie Centrale, Ed. 21/22. Bichkek 2013 – p. 25-40.
- Ostonov 2023* – *Ostonov J.* Buxoro vohasini o'rganish Fransiya-O'zbekiston arxeologik missiyasi haqida (About the French-Uzbekistan archaeological mission to study the Bukhara oasis) // Buxoro tarixi masalalari (eng qadimgi zamonlardan hozirgacha) mavzusidagi xalqaro miqyosdagi ilmiy-

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-5

amaliy konferensiya materiallari (Materials of the international scientific-practical conference on issues of Bukhara history (from the earliest times to the present), Buxoro, 2023. 47-50b

Gorshenina 2012 – Gorshenina S. Les études centrasiatiques // Carnet RESAP-Livre blanc des recherches sur l'Asie et le Pacifique, 17 juillet 2012. [En ligne : <http://resap.hypotheses.org/67>]

Thorez J, Cleuziou J, Fauve A. Les études sur l'Asie Centrale en France, Cahier du GIS N2, Paris 2021

Rante R, Lintz Y. Splendeurs des oasis d'ouzbékistan. Sur les routes caravanieres d'asie centrale. Paris, Editions El Viso, 2022

Römer T. Le Collège de France : quelques données sur son histoire et son caractère propre // L'annuaire du Collège de France, 120, Paris 2023, 627-660. // <https://doi.org/10.4000/annuaire-cdf.19080>)

Poujol C. Cahier d'Asie centrale, 28, Bichkek 2020, 260 p // <https://journals.openedition.org/asiecentrale/4253>

